

Understanding value: the devil's in the details

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[WORLDVIEW]

In our attempt to explore possible solutions for the world's grave environmental problems, our book titled [Better economics for the Earth](#) [1] proposes a new approach to understanding and redefining value. A good explanation is [provided in Tran](#) (2025), which informs us that the current approach to understanding value has been criticized for trying to “put a price tag on nature” without fundamentally challenging the underlying economic paradigm [2].

To further support the process of change, concerning our understanding value, we now introduce [a new paper](#) bearing in mind that “the devil's in the details” [3].

The manuscript can also be read [here](#) [3]

References

- [1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better economics for the Earth: A lesson from quantum and information theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>
- [2] Tran TMA. (2025). Information as the new currency of value. <https://philarchive.org/rec/TRAIAT-4>
- [3] Vuong QH, La VP, Nguyen MH. (2025). Informational entropy-based value formation: A new paradigm for a deeper understanding of value. <http://books.google.com/books/about?id=8SVEEQAAQBAJ>

